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Outside-in: Public-Private Partnerships Upgrading the Institutional Equilibrium in Morocco, the Netherlands and Serbia

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Abstract

In this comparative paper on growing public-private partnerships for skills development in Morocco, the Netherlands and Serbia, we refer to the thematic conference issue: historical pathways of institutional development of skill formation in different orientations and systems to the social justice, market economy and socio-economic development.

Keywords

skills alignment, public-private partnerships, institutional arrangements, innovative education practices

1 Public-private partnership in skills formation

Education systems have high degrees of institutionalisation. When education systems underperform, actors will express their ambition to change practices, especially when there is a need for skilled labour. Fast-changing technological requirements in work processes, a skewed demographic composition, unevenly spread labour mobility and austerity in government spending have all raised the need for public education to adapt.

In Vocational Education and Training (VET)¹ we observe an increasing use of Public-private partnerships (PPPs), which lead to changes towards a new institutional equilibrium. These changes may be initiated by governments or semi-public institutions alone; by the public actors in alliance with companies and educational institutes and schools; and, last but not least, institutional innovation may be spurred by associations, companies and chambers of commerce on a local level.

¹ For the purpose of this paper, we use VET as short for: vocational education, continuous vocational education and training, skills development, skills for work, labour-market oriented education and training, including components of non-formal learning.

We define PPPs for skills development as mechanisms for coordinating action and sharing responsibility for skill production at national, regional or at school level between public and private actors.² Our analysis on VET shows the importance of formulating, designing, financing, managing and/ or sustaining engagements of common interest with a view to producing results at the level of outcomes (impact) in addition to outputs.

As we will illustrate below, we are aware that PPPs in education is a controversial issue because of the risk of privatization of education³, but in this paper we aim to show how a skills challenge or a mismatch between supply and demand does lead to renewal of VET-systems. Our ambition is to analyse the institutional developments that aim to improve the alignment of the demand for skilled labour and the quantity and quality of the labour supply, in response to the above-mentioned challenges. These problems are often wicked; they can have many causes, and improving or solving an issue implies addressing several interconnected conditions, including the existing institutional equilibrium. Overcoming these issues calls for cooperative efforts at different levels of aggregation by companies and schools in a particular branch of the economy, first and foremost in relation to local labour markets, but also in relation to collective skill formation as a whole. Hence, what can be achieved in a particular country is influenced by institutional checks and balances and to the system's resilience and capacity to be permeated by innovative solutions (ETF, 2020a).

We present brief case-studies of the emergence of PPP for vocational skills development in Morocco, Netherlands and Serbia. The three countries have different socio-economic contexts and VET systems, thus we look at specific forms of PPP they have developed in VET against the background of their respective institutional conditions, namely key system governance features and social dialogue tradition and practice. The rationale for comparing three different country contexts lies with their common experience of government and/or companies having failed to invest in skills formation, which subsequently has led to an innovation in partnerships followed by an upgrading of the education system.

We aim to show how the 'outside-in' mechanism works. To this purpose, we show how in a dissimilar social-economic contexts, strategies to enter and improve the existing institutional equilibrium have interesting similarities. Our respondents validated the importance of the new innovative networks of regional cooperation between schools and companies outside the existing public school system in the first instance, whereas afterwards the newly established structure permeated the regular VET system.

2 PPPs for skills development – a paradigm shift

The literature on Public-Private Partnership originates from the analysis of public work and public infrastructure. Roads, dikes, bridges, swimming pools only emerge from public investment and procurement, when markets and states fail and public service provision underperforms. Recent conceptualization of public governance and public policy administration suggests a shift in the conceptualisation of PPPs from the traditional definition that focuses on infrastructure delivery and management to an understanding of PPPs at the level of long-term programme and policy outcomes. This is relevant in the domain of skills production. Bussemeyer and Trampusch (2014) place the political economy of skills production in a development of state-related, market-related and social -partnership based skills systems, but lack a detailed analysis of interaction between markets and states leading to public private partnerships (ETF, 2020a).

² We follow the study of the European Training Foundation (ETF) that monitored progresses in VET systems and policies in 14 countries (ETF, 2020a).

³ One important reference for the critics to PPP in education is the human right approach, see for example: de Koning, M. (2018), Abidjan Principles (2019).

More generally, no adequate definition nor a new consensus on the concept of PPPs exists in the skills domain, as follows from the following three arguments:

- The OECD, World Bank and EIB definitions all reflect PPPs where the main motivation of the private sector to engage in a partnership is direct financial gain. These definitions, which inform the national laws of both groups of countries in the study, do not fit with PPPs geared to outcomes or long-term benefits for society.
- Partnerships are the focus of the 17th Sustainable Development Goal (SDG). However, while the SDGs encourage PPPs as one systemic issue, they do not provide a definition of the concept in education or training.
- PPPs can be perceived as a threat to education, viewed as a public good and a fundamental human right. The PPP model is seen as a vehicle for privatising education supply, bringing concerns about possible failures in quality, equity, accountability and social cohesion. These critiques chiefly concern the sphere of basic and compulsory education, whereas VET and skills development have their own specificity and history of public-private relationships.

From these findings, we seek to reach a more systematic understanding of the scope and functioning of these partnerships, and of their potential to establish a direction for public-private cooperation in VET. This can be framed as a paradigm shift from the New Public Management model that originated in the United Kingdom in the early 1990s to one closer to New Public Governance (Osborne, 2010; Osborne and Stokosch, 2013) and Public Value Creation (Moore, 1995; O'Flynn, 2007).

With this theoretical shift, the notion of value for the stakeholders has emerged to highlight that value is the result of multiple contributions along the chain of value generation. In that perspective, value is rather a collective creation, for it depends on different sources of inputs at different stages. The value for the stakeholder approach argues that the benefits should return to all those concerned. This notion is coupled with a vision of the value creation as long-term process, as opposed to the shareholder value approach that rather focuses on maximising short-term returns for those in the last leg of the value creation process, while it tends to disregard those who contributed earlier on in the entire (longer) value chain (Mazzucato, 2021).

The lenses of the value for the stakeholders' framework make us to consider the learners as relevant stakeholder in the VET and skills development system. The investment in learning programmes is made to generate good quality skills, technical and key competences, relevance for the labour market and personal development that benefit the learner, and eventually the competitiveness and innovation of the enterprise. In this framework, therefore, PPPs in VET are meaningful arrangements if they foster the quality and relevance of skills; in other words, if they generate value for all contributors: the public partner that represent the community or state, the private partner and the learner.

The New Public Governance and Public Value Creation paradigms operated a shift of focus on the outcomes of public expenditure, without neglecting the efficiency. In domains such as VET, indeed programme partnerships offer a means to implement policies if they are outcome-driven, i.e. with states, schools and companies bringing in resources to establish training centres and/or enhancing learning practices in response to technological change and labour market needs. Public-private boundaries have evolved over the past 30 years; however, while the creation of public value is not the sole responsibility of governments, the state should lead on standards of public value delivery set at high level. In order to make PPPs to work, it is fundamental that the public sector possesses due capacities, plays as catalyst, and remains accountable for the value created along the path and policy outcomes.

3 A schematic analysis of PPP-development in three countries.

But how does this work in practice? We distinguish between the emergence of these PPPs and their institutionalization. In the scheme below we define various dimensions of PPPs-emergence and development. We analyse both the type of innovation, the contextual factors as well as the dimensions of the emerging PPPs. Contextual factors include the nature of the existing regulative pattern in a particular country, the degree of centralisation and decentralisation of policy preparation and the existence of social-dialogue. The emergence dimension refers to the source of innovation, the kind of PPP that is established, its resources and form of monitoring and evaluation.

Table 1

Dimensions in PPPs emergence and development: case-study comparison in Morocco, the Netherlands and Serbia

	MOROCCO	NETHERLANDS	SERBIA
TYPE OF INNOVATION			
CASE-SOURCE OF INNOVATION/ LEADERSHIP	(1) DMIs (delegated management institutes), notably the IFMIAs in the automotive sector (2) CMCs, Cités des Métiers et Compétences	Platform Beta technics, later: Katapult	(1) IFVC (2) FACTS (3) E2E (4) HORES
ROLE PPP – KIND OF PPP	Both (1) and (2) are PPPs oriented to VET provision and resources enhancement. The DMIs model was established in the years 2000s. The CMCs are a complementary model of the 2020s	Existing, now in a new manner	(1) Traditional PPP. (2)-(4) VET specific PPP
POLICY CONTEXT			
CENTRALISATION/ DECENTRALISATION OF GOVERNANCE POLICY	Centralised, but decentralisation advancing steadily	Decentralised under a coordinating governance mechanism	(1) Centralised (2) Semi-centralised (3) Semi-centralised (4) Semi-centralised

SOCIAL DIALOGUE	Yes, in place and in TVET is advanced in priority sectors. Employers are active but unions less so.	Yes, but PPPS develop in extended form via top-sector policy	Little to zero
LEGAL ARRANGEMENTS-REGULATIVE CLIMATE	(1) Law on delegated management institutes, March 2006. (2) Roadmap on VET, April 2019, for stronger responsibilities of the regions and involvement of private sector	Conditional	(1) PPP Law and Public Procurement Law (2) & (3) Dual Education Law (4) Adult Education Law
FINANCIAL ARRANGEMENTS INVOLVEMENT INTERNATIONAL PARTNERS	The state finances the infrastructure, the private sector contributes via the national tax on VET. International donors support individual institutes/centres.	EU	(1), (2) & (4) private investments. (3) private investments (40-50%) and donor support (50-60%)
RISK MANAGEMENT-DIVISION OF RISKS AND RISK MANAGEMENT MEASURES	Risks are shared, states grants are based on outputs, monitoring councils are in place. In the case (2), monitoring councils at regional level yet to be established.	Via organized evaluation procedures	Taken predominantly by the private partners
IMPACT OF PPP			
NATURE OF THE RENEWAL	Both (1) and (2) have become stable PPP models.	Pilots, funded by public money with private partnership	(1), (2) & (4) stable and developing. (3) pilot, with a prospective of formalisation
CAPACITY OF PARTNERS AND	Growing capacity of both private and public sector	Growing capacity through funding resources and bringing	Defining the content and provision of

CAPACITY BUILDING MECHANISMS	actors. Capacity to learn lessons and improve. The model (2) is part of broader decentralisation reform, leading to revisit roles and capacities of central and regional levels.	partners together under one roof	training according to the partners' needs; growing capacities of the partners.
MONITORING/ FOLLOW-UP AND SUSTAINABILITY : COSTS/ BENEFITS FOR STAKEHOLDERS	Inter-ministerial cooperation and PPPs are stabilising, in framework of multi-level governance development. Closeness to skilled labour demands, greater autonomy, and accountability mechanisms	Extended exchange, new recruitment opportunities	(1) appropriate goods to be procured. (2)-(4) properly skilled labour force for employers
MONITORING/ FOLLOW-UP SUSTAINABILITY : COSTS/ BENEFITS FOR LEARNERS	(1) tracer studies show high graduate employment rates. (2) in 2023, it was too early to have results	New Experience	(1) extended skills (2)-(4) high job-placement rate

4 The emergence and institutionalisation of PPPs over time

The start of a PPP requires cooperation between public and private actor that engage in common understanding. The establishment of partnership regularly follows a stepwise approach of establishing partnerships: start-up, institutionalisation, consolidation and further evolution. These steps may be speeded up or delayed, or they may occur simultaneously. What we find in each of the three countries under scrutiny in this paper is a quite clear outside-in mechanism.

Stage one: start-up phase of specification and conceptualisation

In the start of a PPP, pioneering and gathering ideas occurs to create something new first outside the current education system, formulating starting principles and allocating resources. At this stage, political entrepreneurs of all kinds will inductively create awareness, specify the main goals and conceptualise the common ambitions of a PPP. Their motivations and preferences include getting the labour market figures and the business case right (at least for the case involved), making themselves better known to potential partners, securing funding and sharing their analysis of the risk distribution for the collaborative project.

Stage two: institutionalisation phase of cooperation by designing and building the PPP model

At this stage, the actors design a more complete concept of cooperation, formulating the exact project targets, building work processes and further developing the division of labour between the management team and the training processes on the workforce, thus providing educational leadership and defining tasks and responsibilities. This stage includes the design of training programmes, the recruitment of students and the implementation of instruction. Once the PPP has been set up, management will plan new activities and monitor the first year's results in accordance with an agenda for the further development of the project in the medium-to-long term.

Stage three: consolidation phase of operating and sustaining the initiative

At this stage, the task is to consolidate engagement and initiatives by enabling and sustaining the operation of the initiative. Apart from the execution of 'running' the project, it will be necessary to strengthen assessment, monitoring and evaluation of activities and to find new financial resources, which may include the growth of sales in order to become independent from the principal subsidies provided by donors. Also likely to become important at this stage is the identification of any potential valorisation of projects, including the management of intellectual property, the spreading of educational results, the application of learning analytics, benchmarking against other initiatives or traditional learning practices, and networking for further exploration. The parties can develop the quality of their own practices and improve the coverage and learning potential for students and companies.

Stage four: Scaling-up and evolution phase of further cooperation leading to integration in the established education structure

In order to spread and sustain an initiative in the future, it will be necessary to continue the engagement of common interests and develop the initiative along new directions of teaching and learning. The cycle of further specification and conceptualisation thus restarts again. This may prompt the exploitation of existing resources as well as further inductive exploration and renewal of the initiative and the start-up of new projects, including the empowerment of staff and students to secure the project's sustainability, undertake the innovation of processes and forge new partnerships.

Here the outside-in mechanism appears: successful initiatives merge due to cross-fertilisation with the 'established educational structure' that appears to become permeable and absorbent in building a learning value chain of projects that appear to be successful and worthwhile continuing. Project evaluation and budget allocation indicate whether the joint experience in the past is strong enough to carry on with the initiative, or whether new forms of public-private entrepreneurship are needed to initiate new practices, that later become integrated in existing school system too.

Morocco: Training Institutes for Professions in the Automotive Sector (IFMIAs), and Cities of Professions and Skills (CMCs)

The creation of IFMIAs for the automotive industry in 2013 was framed by Morocco's National Pact for Industrial Emergence 2009-2015, a strategy to foster key sectors of the economy. The strategy paid due attention to the skills creation and continuous development as a factor for quality employment of individuals and competitiveness of the enterprises. To this end, the government and sector associations established Delegated Management Institutes (DMIs), namely technical and vocational centres of excellence created through state budget and whose management was entrusted to the concerned industry branch. DMIs were also established in other sectors of national relevance, such as the aeronautics, electronics and others.

The IFMIAs are founded by state budget while the private sector contributes indirectly through the national tax on VET. They receive additional funds through conditional grants

depending on the outputs. IFMIAs are established as companies, have autonomy of decision on spending and recruitment and are managed by professionals of the automotive sector through a Board of Directors, a President and a Development Council. Some IFMIAs have pursued ISO 9001 certification of their management practice, adopting continuous improvement and risk management approaches. Accountability and financial autonomy are key principles. A tracer study in 2019, showed graduate employment rates of 88% or more depending on the qualification, in at least two of the institutes.

Since 2019, a further model of PPP for skills is in place in Morocco – the *Cités des Métiers et Compétences* (CMCs). They are an outcome of the enhanced regionalisation policy, which has pushed the devolution of responsibilities on public policies from the central to the sub-national level, namely to the country's 12 regions. The technical and vocational education is embedded in such policy, based on the recognition that proximity to territorial specificities and economic specialisation adds value to skills development. CMCs offer education and training at secondary and post-secondary level, namely *techniciens et techniciens spécialisés*, tuned to each region's specific labour market demands. In early 2023, a total of 7 out of 12 CMCs were built and 3 were operational and effectively providing education.

CMCs are governed by a Board that comprises 3 parties: the employer federation representing the relevant sector, the Office for VET and Employment (OFPPT) and the Regional Council. The CMCs are legally established as companies where the private sector holds 51% of the shares and is Chair of the Board. Such a governance arrangement reflects the strategy of increasing the demand orientation of TVET in a twofold manner: on one hand, the engagement of the private sector in the decision making, far beyond a consultative role, on the other, the territorialisation for the system to cater for the diversity of learning needs across regional labour markets.

A comparison between the DMIs and CMCs models shows complementarity and differences. We observe complementarity whereby DMIs such as the IFMIAs are connected to sectors of national relevance, whereas the CMCs are embedded in the regional economic fabric to address territorial level's demands. The two types of institutions are PPPs and in both cases private sector actors in a given industry play a key role, but there are differences. Notably, CMCs boards comprise three actors, an arrangement that requires greater interaction and responsibility sharing with the public actors – although the private sector holds the majority – compared to the DMIs.

In summary, the PPP approach is relatively recent but progressively gaining space in the TVET system in Morocco. It has started with the DMIs, which have gone through the four stages of development, have expanded to new sectors, have graduated many cohorts of students, and reached financial sustainability. Currently, DMIs have high reputation, education is fee-based but students compete to enrol. Signals point to the full institutionalisation of DMIs, and their success to bring the PPP approach from outside to inside the system. CMCs show that PPPs in VET in Morocco are accepted and are situated at development stage two: they are being institutionalised, with only few having started the very first school year and the monitoring mechanism not yet in place. They introduce a strong regional dimension and, due to their Board composition, may potentially steer greater public and private actor co-work over the teaching and learning process, in comparison to DMIs. Hence, they demonstrate further public-private entrepreneurship, as well as capacity to learn lessons and diversify.

These innovative PPPs have been sustained by social partnership in TVET, which in Morocco is stronger than other countries in Northern Africa and Middle East. In the '90s of last century and the 2000s, social dialogue has been a source of frustration due to lack of solutions to the skill mismatch; however, it has never stopped and eventually led to innovative PPPs, such as the DMIs and CMCs. Within VET, employers engage more actively than employee representatives in the dialogue with the government.

The Netherlands: 160 PPP centres in VET and HPE schools

In the Netherlands, the turn to public-private partnership started in 2010-2011 when a new industrial policy was initiated under the label of the Topsector-approach. Ever since, joint projects have been proposed allowing for new combinations at the border of VET and of HPE between schools and external partners, supported by government agencies. This new approach is characterised by an experimentalist governance approach, though with variation depending on the policy context; in the VET-context the characteristics of cooperation are more bureaucratic in nature, in HPE more network-prone, whereas an increasingly experimentalist governance was probed in both sectors during the course of the 2010s (Moerman, 2020).

The existing private initiatives in *both upper-vocational and higher professional education* have not altered and keep their deep historical roots, originating in cooperative forms and networks originating from the guild structure of the mediaeval period. The 1919 Craft Education Act entailed the first dimensions of partnership in the modern era. After the Second World War, vocational and higher professional education has become well established in two separated systems: a system of senior secondary professional level (MBO), issued by the WEB Act of 1996, and a separate system of higher professional level education (HBO), founded in the WHO-Act of 1986. In the legislative process associated with these most recent reforms, schools were attributed substantial autonomy and within the process of scale enlargement a process of merging and rationalisation of schools has occurred.

These current initiatives of new forms of Public-private partnership aim to connect both upper secondary vocational education and higher professional education with innovations in labour and product markets. Within this overall ambition there are three concrete goals:

1. To increase the number of technical students (mathematics, engineering, science and technology, STEM) and to enhance educational innovation in the context of regional development;
2. To innovate the practice of professions and production processes;
3. To encourage life-long learning.

In order to reach these goals, the PPP-instrument has been chosen, on the supposition that the speed of change needed to enhance innovation in schools, could only be derived with help of external or outside incentives. Three different models have been initiated; Centers for Vocational Craftmanship in VET, Centres of Expertise in HPE, next to a programme for Regional Investments funds in VET. In each of them, in spite of the organizational differences, a returning issue for the PPP-projects is: How to (re)develop the education system to equip young learners (and adults learners) with the right tools and innovation skills (STEM, entrepreneurship, creativity) to succeed in the reality of 21th century labour markets? The centres aim to promote and stimulate innovation in vocational and professional education and to contribute to the transformation of these educational institutes: students solve real-world challenges or questions and work at innovative solutions to strengthen social and economic competitiveness. The cooperation facilitates the access of companies to knowledge development in the educational institutes and vice versa schools are better aware of new technologies and work practices in companies.

The organisational basis for these innovations date back to 2004, when the three of Ministries Economic Affairs, Social Affairs and Education established the Science and Technology Platform (Platform Bèta-Techniek, PBT), with the overall aim to enhance the number of students in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM). Since its start, several recruitment campaigns and programmes for innovative cooperation between companies and education institutes have been initiated and new types of educational programmes have been propagated, to promote technical and technology-oriented education at all levels in all types. In 2019, the Platform Bèta-Techniek (PBT) has been merged into a wider

organization,⁴ whereas the new spin-off Katapult (established in 2016) aims to serve as engine, broker and stimulator to multiply the several initiatives.

The main facilitating task of the platform has been to enhance new cooperative forms of innovation, always in the open environment of schools. The available funds were to be granted for joint proposals outside the primary process of schools and companies. The platform supported the take-off and monitored the performance of the projects which were characterised by ‘open-ended goals’ under a shared framework in which multiple stakeholders interact. Monitoring was crucial for evaluating the endurance of the approach, when the results are too disappointing project need to stop after evaluation of the board.

PPPs have been initiated above all in the domains of the Topsector approach: water management, biobased economy, creative sector and IT, high-tech systems and the like. In a second stage also health care and the basic programmes of VET have become domains for engaging in PPPs. The evidence of about 160 PPP-projects is mixed, especially in the field of live long learning the results are disappointing, whereas the influx of new student in technology sectors has increased somewhat but far less than was hoped for. Notwithstanding in particular sectors success have been reported for the professionalisation and unexpected innovations (Moerman, 2020). In the field of digitalisation for example, projects such as ‘Make IT work’ in Amsterdam and the ‘IT-programme’ in Rotterdam have started from a small initiative and become integrated step-by step in regular vocational education at all levels, whereas the Centre of Expertise in ‘personalised learning with ICT’ (Han university of Applied science) has become a national centre for research of digital learning processes and professionalisation of teachers in all educational sectors. In the recent National Growth Fund competition, Katapult was granted another 250 million Euro for establishing new Public-private partnerships in the Netherlands.

Serbia: Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Cluster FACTS, Education to Employment scheme, and HORES Academy

Even though formal structures have been institutionalised in the Council for Vocational Education and Adult Education, the social partners’ actual influence on decision-making, specifically on VET policy, is limited. In **Serbia**, there is a firm legal basis for PPP development, but social dialogue reflecting the former Yugoslavian economy, is not well-developed in the field of skills development. There appear to be sufficient legal opportunities to create the institutional conditions for PPP in spite of more restricted access to financial resources and limited evidence, motivation and awareness of former traditions of mutual cooperation and joint social partnership.

The PPP cases, which are mainly VET provision-oriented, have developed at the local level in response to labour-force demand. One case, the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops (IFVC), is production-oriented, where the development of skills is an associated need. Two of the cases (Cluster FACTS, which is related to the preparation of specialists for the fashion industry, and E2E, an innovative scheme for the transition from education to employment) have proceeded in accordance with the Law on Dual Education. The other case (HORES Academy, training specialists in the hospitality sector) is based on the Law on Adult Education. The motivation of both parties – private and public – is strong in all of the PPPs and their level of sustainability is high.

The case of **IFVC** is in fact a classic PPP where the private partner provides services to the public party and remuneration is linked to the performance. However, for this cooperation the

⁴ In 2019, three separate organizations all active in the technological domain PBT, TechniekTalent.nu and TecWijzer are being merged into a joint ‘Platform Talent voor Technologie’ (Platform Talent for Technology).

skills development is not an objective *per se*, but a concomitant need for reaching the primary goal related to business. IFVC produces and imports high quality seeds of different crops but due to limited plots of own land, it is unable to ensure the volumes demanded by the market. Therefore, IFVC orders small farms and individual producers to grow the crops on their lands. Institute provides the partners with seeds which are only to be used for growing the plants. No other means are provided by IFVC. The farmers make their own investments for purchasing fertilisers, medications, water, energy, machinery and tools beforehand, and allocate considerable plots of their land, thus taking considerable risks. At the same time, for ensuring necessary quality of the produced seeds, the Institute, in advance, organises the farmers' capacity building which covers all agro-technology aspects and processes related to growing the ordered plants. In addition, IFVC trains the farmers also for more productive growing of other crops.

The Fashion Apparel Cluster Serbia (Cluster **FACTS**) is an Association which unites 20 private companies from the fashion and garment production sector, three higher educational institutions, and a Fashion Platform of young fashion designers. FACTS promotes the member companies' export and brings together the producers (and designers) and the education sector. Initiative of cooperation with education comes from the private sector and is conditioned by a considerable shortage of skilled labour force. Under dual education scheme, practical training of more than 100 students from 3 VET schools (data for 2019) is organised at the FACTS's member companies and covers at least 60% of the total amount of curricula. This dual training is a part formal education, therefore, the VET schools are not simply recipients of the private sector sponsorship but fully-fledged partners who also bear responsibilities. During the internship, the trainees are paid by the companies who decide the amount. One of them pays the student ~45 € per month, provides free lunch and transportation. Selection of the students is also done by the employers. Some students are provided with opportunity to be interns in the member-companies' shops, sometimes even with higher remuneration.

The Project *Education to Employment* ("E2E") is a joint initiative of the Serbian and Swiss Governments who are co-funders of the project with almost equal shares. One of the project's components is focused on skills development, specifically of unemployed young people through provision of the German model of dual education, adapted to the local conditions. The project has a specific architecture: in every region, local partners (usually civil society institutions) are selected and play a role of mediators ("Brokers") between the E2E and the local partners, particularly those who provide dual education courses. The Brokers are responsible e.g. for promoting the project and its activities, for attracting and mobilising youth to be involved in those activities, for training the practical training mentors, as well as for monitoring and evaluating the trainings. Theoretical part of the training is delivered by accredited VET providers (public VET schools or any authorised private training providers), while the practical part is implemented in the private companies.

In order to launch a course, E2E shall receive application from a local "consortium" consisting of a VET provider and a company. Development of training proposals and preparation of applications is assisted by the regional Brokers. If the proposal is assessed as relevant and credible, E2E authorises the Broker to conclude a formal agreement with the VET provider and the company. Then, the training is financed from the E2E Opportunity Fund, again through the Broker. This allows the latter to develop their capacities, to become more financially independent and influential, and also motivated to attract and promote more courses.

HORES is a Business Association for Hotel and Restaurant that associates under its umbrella hotels, restaurants, casinos, suppliers and other entities, and protects and promotes the common and professional interests of its members. Permanent shortage of qualified labour force in the hotel and catering business impelled HORES to establish its own training institution – the HORES Academy. The main activity of the Academy is one-day and multi-day seminars

and longer-term courses for sector-specific occupations which are free to the participants. Training programmes of the HORES Academy are developed in close collaboration with employers aiming to correspond to their needs, requirements and preferences. At the same time, the trainings are organised on the basis of the Adult Education Law and the Ministry of Education has provided HORES Academy with accreditation. This means a possibility to apply for funding using the calls of the Ministry of Tourism.

Summarising, it can be stated that although the discussed four cases are rather different by their structure and by the types of involved parties, they have a number of similarities: 1) partnerships were established either at the initiative of the private partners or the latter were heavily engaged at different stages and aspects; 2) the relations between the parties are stable, clearly contracted and derived from the mutual interest; 3) all cases lead to considerable results in terms of skills development; 4) the private partners directly invest their own funds and provide also in-kind contribution, they also take a considerable part of risk; 5) certain accountability to the public partner is in place. At the same time, any solid monitoring and/or evaluation schemes seem still lacking.

5 Conclusions: outside-in mechanisms in PPPs

When we aim to understand processes of innovation in education we should be aware of the regularly conservative nature of teaching and learning as an ongoing practice that is highly institutionalised in curricula and annual planning. Education systems are thus not easy to change. They consist of vested interests and routines that cannot be altered on a daily basis.

The nature of the cases we discuss in this paper is innovative. The actors bring in resources and new combination of interaction and responsibility in VET in the form of capacity building to generate ideas, to monitor outcomes and to create something new. What we show in this paper is that PPPs that have been on the brink of emerging ten years ago, now prove to be part of the educational system. PPPs can be seen as new initiatives for providing training in a particular region, sector or country, next to ongoing educational practices.

These innovations are to be regarded as bottom-up process. They appear to follow a relative chaotic pattern in local areas but lead to convergence in a later stage. Within varying time horizons, actors engage in three key issues that prove to be relevant: the cooperation dilemmas: how to get started; the requirements and conditions of government legislation and coordination: how to get institutionalised; and the nature of experimental governance: how to become enduring and continuous.

The various stages of the model described earlier in this chapter can be seen in each of the three countries: start-up, institutionalisation, consolidation and evolution. In the first stage of pioneering, a new initiative develops next to or outside from the established educational practice. Both public and private partners need to be prepared to take risks and invest to achieve joint public value that is considered legitimate. The investment lies not only in financial resources, but also in time and human resources and often in equipment, tools and materials as well. This can be beneficial for one or both of the actors, and eventually create impact on the legal, institutional and financial arrangements i.e. changes at system level.

Depending on the political climate and economic cycle, the start-up period will sometimes need to be quite long and it may be hardly visible to the general public. Broker organisations or individuals may pave the way by solving all kinds of emerging problems, helping to set up new adhocracies or innovative organisations by attracting human resources and facilitating team-building, convening and hosting meetings and events, and facilitating social collaboration practices. Underlying agreements and memoranda of understanding can be developed. Helpful incentives may be provided, such as subsidies for pilot programmes that are subsequently ranked and rewarded to enhance recognition and further develop policies and regulations. In

short, political entrepreneurs will play a host of roles as they create a platform for other actors to join.

It should be noted that ambitions will change at a certain point if no progress is achieved. Some initiatives may be sustained, while others will cease or receive a new start. The decision may be taken by the participating organisations or by the government to stop and restart a project, or to initiate something new. More broadly, the practice of social dialogue in VET offers a positive background to innovative PPPs for skills; even in contexts like Morocco and Serbia where the lack of results in social dialogue had been for years a source of frustration.

The relevance of this paper for further study

The development of PPPs in three countries is relevant also to newest developments, such as the green and digital transitions. At UN and EU levels goals have been set, and governments have approved policies and legislation, however a huge deal of innovation is necessary to implement the twin transition, requiring bottom-up initiative besides the strategies and legislation. There are no unique solutions to innovation, but stakeholder collaboration and creativity is a necessary ingredient.

References

- Abidjan Principles (2019). Guiding Principles on the human rights obligations of States to provide public education and to regulate private involvement in education. Retrieved from <https://www.abidjanprinciples.org/en/principles/overview>
- Baccaro, L. & Howell, C. (2017). *Trajectories of neoliberal transformation: European industrial relations since the 1970s*. Cambridge, New York, Melbourne, Delhi and Singapore: Cambridge University Press
- Busemeijer, M. & Trampusch, C. (2011). *The political economy of collective skill formation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press
- Ebbinghaus, B. & Weishaupt, J.T. (eds.). (2021). *Crisis corporatism or corporatism in crisis? The role of social partners in managing Europe's Great Recession*. London: Routledge.
- European Training Foundation, (2018). *Reforms in vocational education and training in ETF partner countries*. Torino, Italy. Retrieved from Reforms in vocational education and training in ETF partner countries: A cross-country digest of reform implementation and risks | ETF (europa.eu)
- European Training Foundation (2020a). *Public-Private Partnerships for Skills Development. A governance perspective*. Volume I and Volume II. Torino, Italy. Retrieved from Public-private partnerships for skills development: A governance perspective – Volume I. Thematic overview, ETF (europa.eu) Public-private partnerships for skills development: A governance perspective – Volume II. Case studies, ETF (europa.eu)
- European Training Foundation (2020b). *Policies for human capital development. An ETF Torino Process assessment*. Torino, Italy. Retrieved from POLICIES FOR HUMAN CAPITAL DEVELOPMENT IN SERBIA, ETF (europa.eu)
- Klein, E.H. (2010). Public-private partnerships: deciphering meaning, message and phenomenon. In G. A., Hodge, C., Greve, & A. E., Boardman (eds.). *International handbook of public-private partnerships* (pp. 68-80). Cheltenham, UK and Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar
- Koning, de M., (2018). Public-private partnerships in education assessed through the lens of human rights. In G., Steiner-Khamsi, & A., Draxler (eds). *The state, business and education*, (pp. 169-188). Cheltenham, UK and Northampton, MA: Edward Elgar. Retrieved from The State, Business and Education – Public-Private Partnerships Revisited | Elgar Online: The online content platform for Edward Elgar Publishing
- Mazzucato, M., (2021). *Mission economy: a moonshot guide to change capitalism*. London, UK: Allen Lane

- Moerman, P. (2020). *Governance regimes and problem-solving capacity: public-private partnerships in Dutch vocational and higher education*. Dissertation. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University
- Moore, M.H. (1995). *Creating public value: strategic management in government*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press
- O'Flynn, J., (2007). From New Public Management to Public Value: Paradigmatic Change and Managerial Implications. *Australian Journal of Public Administration*, 66: 353-366.
- Osborne, D., & Gaebler, T. (2013). *Reinventing government: how the entrepreneurial spirit is transforming the public sector*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- Osborne, S. P. (2000). *Public -private partnership: theory and practice in international perspective*. London, UK: Routledge

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